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A GAMIFIED PHYSICS CLASS FOR ENGINEERING COURSES: ELECTRICAL POTENTIAL

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ABSTRACT

Gamification can be defined as the use of game design elements, in a non-game context. This work reports the gamification of an Experimental Physics class, dealing with the concepts of Electric Potential and Electric Field, offered to Engineering students. The narrative was based on the strategy to get out of a bumped car, on the verge of fire and electrified due to a fall of a high voltage cable. We have adopted a Flipped Classroom approach to introduce theoretical contents through videos, verified by quizzes. All activities were scored and after successfully completed, gave access to the technical content of the experiment. The equipment description, electric circuits, gathering and data analysis were made available in videos. The solution to the initial problem was simulated in the laboratory and theoretically justified. The students reported great engagement and interest concerning the class. More than acquiring technical knowledge and simulating a real situation, they were proofed in situations that required decision and assertiveness to solve unexpected problems. Gamification showed to be a suitable methodology capable of engaging students, giving them more than just technical information, but also the opportunity to develop soft skills.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Gamification is defined as the use of game design elements, in a context that does not necessarily contain games [1]. Despite its increasing use in the corporate world [2-3], few applications have been done in Higher Education [4]. Gamification applied to Education is a methodology that seeks to engage students to acquire knowledge actively and, generally in an enjoyable way, making the learning process more attractive and lasting longer [5]. In Higher Education (HE), enjoyment is a secondary issue, since the emphasis is on meaningful learning and citizen consciousness since the objective is to prepare a whole professional, in academic and socio-emotional terms [6].

The game elements used in a learning activity vary according to the objectives and profile of the participants [7]. The most common are scores, rewards, and badges. Collaboration and competition, success and frustration, suspense, empowerment, gains and losses, social recognition are other viable elements. However, not all these elements need to be included in the same gamified activity. In an academic discipline, usually subdivided into topics, each one can be explored with different dynamics and elements.

Students are often introduced to Physics in the first academic years together with Mathematics and Chemistry. Usually, these students are very young and still immature, lacking in technical skills, making a multidisciplinary approach like PBL (Problem-Based Learning) very restricted. However, they are very open to new experiences and challenges.

How to teach Physics interestingly, connecting theoretical concepts to real cases, giving students hard and soft skills, while keeping them engaged while connecting their expectations to the professional world?

In this work, we report a pilot study concerning a hybrid methodology implemented in a class concerning Electric Potential and Electric Field, within the Experimental Physics discipline, offered to students of the 2nd year of Engineering courses.

The guiding questions (GQ) for this study were:

(GQ1) Is it feasible to apply gamification and flipped classroom in an experimental discipline, considering the usability of the platform (Moodle), quality, clarity and customization of content, as well the rhythm of study?

(GQ2) How is the students' acceptance of linking the access to contents, with their academic performance?

(GQ3) Is it possible to learn theoretical concepts and acquire technical skills in a gamified class?

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Gamification and Flipped Classroom

The storytelling was based on the strategy for safely getting out of a bumped car, on the verge of burning, and electrified due to the fall of a high voltage cable. Before the experimental activity (pre-lab) we have adopted a Flipped Classroom methodology to introduce theoretical contents (Electric Potential and Electric Field) through videos, verified by quizzes. Gamification was implemented in all activities carried out by students (access to texts and videos, quizzes, participation in forums and social networks, questionnaires, and feedback), being scored by grades, points (XP) and virtual currencies (zcoin). We have implemented the class using the Moodle platform. Virtual currencies (zcoin) and points (XP) could be implemented through Stash and Level Up plugins, respectively. Two formative quizzes (equipotentials curves: general ideas and theory) were applied and when answered with performance greater than 60%, within two attempts, students were entitled to virtual keys and zcoins, besides grades. Once obtained the 2 keys, they got access to the content of the experimental activities (objectives, experimental protocol, technical report model), finishing the pre-lab level. Students who were unable to obtain the 2 keys were submitted to new quizzes (continued recovering) until keys were earned. During pre-lab, optional contents (diversified technical information, engineering cases, and curiosities) were offered, in order to customize the class. Pre-lab level could be done anywhere (through Moodle) before the experimental activities. To help students to manage their rhythm we have suggested a schedule for activities.

After finishing experimental activities, students were required to write a structured but concise technical report (post-lab) and answered some questionnaires to evaluate the implemented hybrid methodology.

Grades obtained in quizzes (pre-lab) and in the technical report (post-lab) were used to compose the final class grade, acting as an indicator for approval in the course. The points (XP) were used only to rank students (top-5 list), acting as a competitive drive. The currencies (zcoin) were saved to be used in trading benefits in the final exam, acting as an immediate merit recognition (completion of an activity), further a facilitating agent in the execution of the final exam (expectation of success).

The equipment description, electric circuits, data collection and analysis were made available through videos, verified by quizzes. Motivating questions were asked to stimulate students' reasoning and make them more alert to details of experimental practice and interpretation of results. Thus, students have presented themselves to the experimental activity having already studied the theoretical foundations of the phenomenon, the experimental protocol and instigated by motivating questions and relevant doubts.

2.2 Experimental Activities

During the pre-lab level, students were instructed on how to determine equipotential lines produced by 2 large electrodes immersed in a water tank, connected to an AC source (12V). However, in the experiment (lab level), a third electrode, disconnected and just immersed into the tank, was added to the experimental set, aiming to produce stress in students. The new electrode simulated another car, near to the electrified one: could these passengers get out the car in safe? Since the students were prepared and were confident to deal with 2 electrodes, the objective was to remove them from the comfort zone, presenting them to an unexpected difficulty. Thus, they could observe their reactions and attitudes, while solving the new version of the problem. Once the map of equipotential curves was determined, the solution to the initial problem (leaving an electrified car) was discussed and simulated, as well theoretically justified. Having students arrived at the laboratory already instructed (pre-lab level), the class could be focused on solving and discussing the experiment and similar practical situations.

2.3 Data collection and assessment

Students' learning was assessed through two quizzes (pre-lab) and a technical but concise report (post-lab), while their participation through points (XP) and coins (zcoin). Overall considerations about the methodology were assessed through anonymous questionnaires, by open and closed questions (Likert scale). Closed questions were divided into 3 groups: (G1) structure and platform's usability; (G2) restrictions to open contents; (G3) confidence level regarding physical concepts. Open questions collected impressions about the concise reports and general suggestions.

This pilot experiment was applied to 22 students (3rd academic semester on Industrial and Civil Engineering) during the 1st semester of 2019, on the course Experimental Physics (2 hours/week, 15 weeks, 30 hours). This article reports the class concerning Electric Potential and Electric Field, which experimental activity had aimed at determining equipotential lines due to two electrodes, immersed in a water tank. The class had been scheduled to be performed during one week: 6 days as a pre-lab level and 1 day to run the experiment (lab) and write a concise report (post-lab level).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data gathered from anonymous questionnaires made possible to obtain answers to our 3 guiding questions. We present here the results through the average values (axis values, on the figures and numbers within parentheses, on the text) to indicate the central trend of these data, without standard deviations, since data do not follow a normal distribution. Only the time spent by students to prepare for the experimental class is indicated in the format (mean \pm standard deviation).

Students reported they have spent (2.2 ± 0.8) hours to gain access to the laboratory contents (be approved on 2 quizzes) and to prepare for the experimental class (pre-lab level). This result cannot be interpreted rigorously, since such time may have been shared with other activities and distractions. However, it suggests that the required preparation time (flipped classroom approach) is feasible, even considering that students have an average weekly workload, inside classroom and laboratories, of 30 hours.

The first group of closed questions (G1) dealt with the GQ1, that is, how feasible is gamification for an experimental course. Figure 1 summarizes these results.

Fig1. GQ1: Feasibility of gamification in an experimental discipline, using Moodle. Likert scale: averaged values. Range: (1: unfeasible) to (5: very feasible)

Despite Moodle is not a platform fitted to gamification, its useability was not a problem (4.3). The narrative (getting out of an electrified car) was very well accepted (4.7). The students commented that it was a realistic situation and getting out in safe would require a quick and correct decision. Also, it dramatized very clearly the concept of electric potential and difference of potential. The mandatory (4.5) and optional (4.5) contents delivered were considered clear and consistent with the class theme. The optional contents allowed some customization since they were diversified and complementary to the theme. Also, they have established a meaningful correlation between physical concepts and real applications in Engineering. The rhythm of daily study and division of contents, suggested by the professor, was well evaluated (4.5). However, there was no strict control over the time of access to the contents, making it impossible to verify whether they were accessed daily (as suggested by the teacher) or in an accumulated way (last minute). These results have indicated that it is feasible to apply gamification and flipped classroom in an experimental discipline, using the Moodle platform.

The second group (G2) assessed the use of grades obtained in quizzes to provide students access to the laboratory's content. The use of quizzes to reinforce the video's content proved to be effective since it facilitates the perception and understanding of aspects that are not normally observed by students (formative assessment). The possibility of reviewing the video, after answering quizzes, favors attention and

perception of technical and conceptual details. Graded quizzes were well accepted (4.2) but their use to restrict access to new content had some rejection (3.8). It is important to note that all students have gained access to the contents of the laboratory. Even so, some expressed the opinion that such a restriction is not interesting, nor does it help students' development. When they were asked about their own dedication to studies, the average grade was 3.6 (figure 2).

Fig2. GQ2: Restrictions to access contents. Likert scale: averaged values. Range: (1: disagree completely) to (5: agree completely). Range(*): (1: no dedication) to (5: too much dedication).

Some students did not like to be evaluated, nor to have their progress restricted by grades. However, some recognize that they did not dedicate themselves hardly to studies. This result seems to indicate that some students believe that they should progress in the discipline, regardless of their performance or dedication. Undoubtedly, any evaluation mechanism is susceptible to criticism and limitations. However, not evaluating and allowing automatic progression is also a questionable criterion, especially when we want to prepare a good professional.

The third group (G3) dealt with the student's confidence level regarding the acquisition of technical knowledge and experimental skills. Students stated they were confident about the procedures to get out of an electrified car (4.5), about how to get closer to such accident (4.5), how to use a voltmeter (4.4) and to define the difference of potential (4.5) and equipotential lines (4.5). On a lower level (3.9), how to define the Electric Field (figure 3).

Fig3.

GQ3: Confidence level regarding technical knowledge and experimental skills. Likert scale: averaged values. Range: (1: very unsure) to (5: very confident).

These results, together with those 2 quizzes, indicate that the academic aims have been achieved. But they also indicated that the electric field concept needs to be better worked out, especially its mathematical relationship (gradient operator) with the electric potential and its physical meaning.

Open questions were formulated concerning (1) their opinion on the concise technical reports, (2) their impressions and self-evaluation and (3) suggestions to improve the class. The model of concise reports was praised and well accepted by all, who reported that they could be more objective and focused on the most relevant concepts and methods. Also, editing concise reports was faster, making this task more attractive and effective. To be concise and clear is a desired attitude in professional life. Students reported that the applied methodology can foster their academic performance. Part of this result can be associated with the mere fact that gamification is a novelty, regardless of any methodological value. However, the global analysis of the results indicates that acceptance of the methodology goes beyond the aspect of novelty or curiosity. The students stated the methodology can prepare them as a better professional also helping in personal development. This indicates that would be possible to promote meaningful learning and connections with the professional tasks, while developing soft skills, even in a Physics class. No suggestions were made! This seems to indicate that students are open to new methodologies and felt respected by the initiative. However, it seems that they do not yet perceive themselves as co-responsible for learning, remaining still in a passive position, although different from that typical of the traditional teaching model.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The students reported and demonstrated in the laboratory, good engagement and interest in the class. It is relevant to point out that physics classes are not usually considered pleasant, nor with easy content to be assimilated or associated with real case situations. The hybrid methodology here presented could foster the acquisition of technical knowledge (methods and physical concepts) associated with socio-emotional practices (achievement of goals, work under pressure, solving unexpected problems, group discussion, focus, etc.), from an interesting and realistic narrative (get out of an electrified car). Further, since students have arrived prepared at the laboratory it allowed a fast and full execution of the experiment and has fostered wide discussions, from concepts to applications in engineering.

These results have indicated that gamification is a feasible methodology to be applied in an experimental discipline, using the Moodle platform, without losing quality in theoretical content or practical skills, in addition to pleasing students. It represents a potential impact on engineering education, since physics classes are often classified as too theoretical and uncorrelated to real problems, inadequate to prepare engineers. However, it is important to stress that gamification or any hybrid

methodology must be changed every two or three classes, to keep students motivated and to avoid their return students to a comfort zone.

It is not possible to state whether there has been any socio-emotional development, since the classroom is not the appropriate place for effective training or assessment, and such a statement would require a long-term study. However, the mere mention that this aspect is relevant to the professional life and was considered within a Physics class, is already capable of attracting students' attention to the issue (soft skills) and to Physics (meaningful knowledge). Also, it reinforces how important are an active learning methodology and instructional design orientated to professional formation, not only in delivering information.

The trading of benefits using virtual currencies (zcoins) was performed only at the end of the course, outside the context of this article. This proposal was very well accepted and meant an extrinsic stimulus, to increase student engagement.

The hybrid methodology implemented (flipped classroom and gamification) proved to be a good way to engage students, giving them, in addition to academic knowledge, the opportunity to think about soft skills. It must be stressed that this pilot experience was performed in the 3rd academic semester when students are still running the basic disciplines, with few contacts with Engineering contents. Furthermore, it must be observed that newcomer students usually are open to new experiences and are very enthusiastic about active methodologies, despite the previous experience with traditional and passive education. It suggests that basic disciplines must be designed to be considered as key elements in Engineering Education, not only to deliver technical information but to established robust grounds for a good professional!

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